

Conference Abstract

The pathway of molecular methods from research to routine use

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Abstract

In this talk I explore how to advance molecular methods from tools in the research domain to routine use in national biomonitoring. I outline the necessity of common guidance, networks, international pilot studies and cooperation with officials to achieve the goal of method uptake into routine use. Lastly, I will explain the role that international method standardization plays in speeding up the uptake process of molecular methods into routine biomonitoring.

Keywords

molecular methods, pilot studies, validation, standardization , CEN, ISO, biomonitoring

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